

4-Quinazolones: III. Synthesis of some Furoquinazolones

S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury

The synthesis of 2,2'-dimethyl-6-methoxy/hydroxy-3-phenylfuro [4',5':7,8] quinazolin-4(3H)-ones and 2'-methyl-6-methoxy/hydroxy-2,3-diphenylfuro[4', 5':7,8] quinazolin-4(3H)-ones is described.

Furoquinazolones represent a condensed heterocyclic system which has not been so far reported in the literature. Our interest¹ on fused ring compounds derived from 4-quinazolones prompted us to undertake the synthesis of some angular furoquinazolones. Kaufman² has developed a method for the synthesis of furocoumarins which involves the use of a blocking group to prevent the migration of the allyl group to the alternative *ortho* position in the Claisen rearrangement of an allyloxycoumarin. The product has then been used in building a furan ring. Adaptation of this procedure for our purpose requires developing a furan ring on preformed quinazolones, and therefore 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (IV) was considered as the most suitable starting material. Since the nitro substituent is *ortho* oriented to the carboxyl group, the nitrogen ring of the quinazolone system can be readily formed to give 6-methoxy-7-allyloxyquinazolones. The methoxyl group can then serve as a blocking group in the Claisen rearrangement to furnish appropriate intermediates for the synthesis of angular furoquinazolones. The synthetic sequence outlined has been realised and we now report the preparation of 2,2'-dimethyl-6-methoxy/hydroxy-3-phenylfuro (4', 5': 7, 8) quinazolin-4(3H)-ones and 2'-methyl-6-methoxy/hydroxy-2,3-diphenylfuro (4',5':7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-ones.

4-Allyloxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (I), obtained by the interaction of *either* vanillin with allyl bromide in the presence of potassium carbonate in DMF or the sodium salt of vanillin with allyl bromide, on oxidation with silver oxide afforded 4-allyloxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid (II) which was nitrated to yield 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (IV). It was also prepared alternatively by nitration of I and oxidation of the resulting 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-nitrobenzaldehyde (III) with Jones reagent³. Attempts to oxidise III with silver oxide under variety of conditions unaccountably failed as intractable products were obtained⁴. The orientation of the nitro group in IV was determined by its m p. 155-156° differing from that (194°) of its 2-nitro isomer⁴; and transformation into the corresponding quinazolin-4(3H)-ones. IV was reduced with sodium dithionite to 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (V), which on treatment with acetic anhydride gave 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid (VI), and with benzoyl chloride in the presence of sodium bicarbonate afforded 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzoic acid (VII). By the action

1. Preceding paper, Part II., B. D. Singh and D. N. Chaudhury.
2. K. D. Kaufman and L. R. Worden, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 117 and later papers.
3. K. Bowden, I. M. Heilbron, E. R. H. Jones and B. C. L. Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 39.
4. Unpublished work in this laboratory.

I ; R = H, R ₁ = CHO	V ; R = NH ₂ , R ₁ = COOH
II ; R = H, R ₁ = COOH	VI ; R = NHCOCH ₃ , R ₁ = COOH
III ; R = NO ₂ , R ₁ = CHO	VII ; R = NHCOPh, R ₁ = COOH
IV ; R = NO ₂ , R ₁ = COOH	

of aniline in the presence of phosphorus trichloride in boiling toluene, VI was converted into 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) and VII into 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX). The latter was also obtained in superior yield by an alternative way. On refluxing with acetic anhydride, VII

VIII ; R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = allyl; R ₃ = H
IX ; R = Ph; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = allyl; R ₃ = H
XI ; R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = H; R ₃ = allyl
XII ; R = Ph; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = H; R ₃ = allyl
XIII ; R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = acetyl; R ₃ = allyl
XIV ; R = Ph; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = acetyl; R ₃ = allyl
XV ; R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = acetyl; R ₃ = CH ₂ Br.CHBr.CH ₂
XVI ; R = Ph; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = acetyl; R ₃ = CH ₂ Br.CHBr.CH ₂

furnished 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (X), identical with the specimen obtained by the interaction of 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (V) with benzoyl chloride in pyridine. On treatment with aniline in chloroform, X yielded IX. Claisen rearrangement of VIII and IX in boiling diethylaniline gave 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI) and 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII) respectively. Subsequent acetylation with acetic anhydride in pyridine furnished the corresponding acetyl derivatives XIII and XIV, which reacted with one molar equivalent of bromine to produce 7-acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV) and 7-acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-6-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI) respectively. These were converted to fourquinazolones by the methods given below.

XVII; R = R₁ = CH₃

XVIII; R = CH₃; R₁ = H

XIX; R = Ph; R₁ = H

XX; R = Ph; R₁ = CH₃

XXI; R = R₁ = CH₃

XXII; R = Ph; R₁ = CH₃

XXIII; R = Ph; R₁ = BrCH₂

Transformation of XV to furoquinazolinone was effected by the method of Kaufman.² Refluxing XV for two hours in alcoholic potassium hydroxide resulted in simultaneous dehalogenation and cyclisation to yield 2,2'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3-phenylfuro (4', 5' : 7,8) quinazolin-4-(3H)-one (XVII) as the major product together with a little alkali-soluble compound identified as 2,2'-dimethyl-6-hydroxy-3-phenylfuro(4',5' : 7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII), formed by partial demethylation. On methylation with diazomethane XVIII was converted into XVII. The demethylation was, however, complete on prolonged treatment of XV with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and XVIII was isolated as the sole product.

XVII was also prepared by an alternative route. On heating with hydrobromic acid according to the method of Claisen⁵ XI was cyclised without demethylation to 2', 3'-dihydro-2, 2'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3-phenylfuro (4', 5' : 7, 8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XXI) which on dehydrogenation with palladium-charcoal furnished XVII.

Cyclisation of XVI, however, did not readily give the expected furoquinazolinone XX. Unlike its 2-methyl analogue (XV), XVI when refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide for two hours gave a small amount of an alkali insoluble bromine-containing compound; from the residual alkaline solution 2'-methyl-6-hydroxy-2,3-diphenylfuro (4', 5' : 7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIX) was isolated as the major product, formed by complete demethylation during cyclisation. Methylation of XIX with diazomethane furnished 2'-methyl-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro (4', 5' : 7, 8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XX). The neutral bromo product melted at 220-230°. Although a sharply melting sample of this compound was never obtained for elemental analysis, it may be 2'-bromomethyl-2', 3'-dihydro-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylfuro (4', 5' : 7, 8)-quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XXIII). Such formulation is deduced from analogy with the formation of 2-bromomethyl-2, 3-dihydro-8H-furo (3, 2-h) (1) benzopyran-8-one⁶ from 8-acetoxy-7-(2',3'-dibromopropyl) coumarin and of 2-bromomethylcoumaran⁷ from 2-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl) phenyl acetate under similar condition.

In contrast to its 2-methyl analogue (XI), the cyclisation of XII with hydrobromic acid or pyridine hydrochloride according to the method of Claisen⁵ failed to yield the dihydrofuro compound XXII as intractable products were obtained.

5. L. Claisen and E. Tietze, *Ber.*, 1925, **58B**, 275.

6. K. D. Kaufman and W. E. Russey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, **27**, 670.

7. R. Adams and R. E. Rindfus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 648.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s and b.p.s are uncorrected. Organic extracts were dried with Na_2SO_4 . Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°.

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde*(I). It was prepared by modifying the published procedure⁸. (a) Allyl bromide (6.8 ml; 0.08 mole) was added to a suspension of Na-salt of vanillin (13.92 g; 0.08 mole) in DMF (50 ml) at room temperature, shaken vigorously for 1 hr when a homogenous solution was obtained and kept overnight. It was poured into water (150 ml), acidified with 2N HCl and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with 0.1N NaOH, water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent yielded I as viscous dark yellow liquid (16.4 ml; 20.24 g), b.p. 200-220°. (lit⁸ b.p. 210-220°). At the b.p. a sample rearranged to 5-allyl-4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, m.p. 83-84° after crystallisation from EtOH (lit⁸ m.p. 86°).

(b) A mixture of vanillin (12.16 g; 0.08 mole), K_2CO_3 (10 g), allyl bromide (6.8 ml; 0.08 mole) in DMF (25 ml) was shaken vigorously for 1 hr when a homogenous solution obtained. It was left overnight, poured into water (150 ml) and worked up as in (a) to yield I (16.2 ml; 20 g) b.p. 200-220°.

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-nitrobenzaldehyde* (III). I (5 g; 4.5 ml) was added dropwise with stirring during 1 hr to conc. HNO_3 (25 ml; d, 1.42) at 10-15°. After the addition, the reaction mixture was stirred for a further period of 0.5 hr, the temperature being not allowed to rise above 15°. It was then poured into crushed ice (250 g), vigorously agitated and the yellow solid that separated was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. Two crystallisations from EtOH furnished III as yellow needles (5.6 g; 92%), m.p. 129-130°. (Found: C, 55.5; H, 4.3; N, 6.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C, 55.7; H, 4.6; N, 5.9%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxybenzoic acid* (II). To a suspension of (a) Ag_2O (1.5 g) in 4% aq. NaOH (20 ml) or (b) AgNO_3 (2.5 g) in water (25 ml) and 15% aq. NaOH (5 ml), was added I (1 g) and heated for 4 hr. on water bath when the Ag mirror formed completely disintegrated. It was filtered and the filtrate acidified with conc. HCl to give a precipitate which was filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from dil. MeOH afforded II as colorless needles (1 g; 93%), m.p. 170-171°. (Found C, 63.6; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.7%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid* (IV). (a) To conc. HNO_3 (20 ml; d, 1.42) at 8-10°, II (2 g) was added with stirring portionwise so that the addition of each instalment followed the dissolution of the preceding one. After a clear solution obtained at the end of the addition, it was stirred for 2 hr, the temperature being maintained at 8-10°. A little of the nitro compound separated during this period. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice when a pale yellow precipitate was obtained. Next day, it was filtered, washed with water, dissolved in 10% aq. NaOH and filtered from a little insoluble material. The filtrate was acidified with 2N HCl and the solid that precipitated was collected, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum gave IV as colorless rhombic plates (1.6 g; 75%), m.p. 155-156°. (Found: C, 51.9; H, 4.1;

N, 5.8. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$ requires C, 52.1 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 5.5%). The solid which is insoluble in aq. NaOH had m.p. 151-152° after crystallisation from EtOH. The quantity being small no attempt was made to identify it.

(b) Jones reagent³ was prepared by dissolving CrO_3 (26.7 g) in conc. H_2SO_4 (23 ml) and water (40 ml), and diluting to 100 ml.

The reagent (4 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of III (2 g) in pure Me_2CO (25 ml) when an orange brown coloration persisted. It was kept overnight and after dilution with water (30 ml) extracted with ether (20 ml×3), the extract shaken with 10% KOH aq. (15 ml×3). The alkaline layer, on acidification, gave colorless precipitate which on crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum furnished IV (1.27 g ; 60%), m.p. 155-156°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as in (a).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid*(V). To a solution of IV (1.5 g) in 10% KOH aq. (15 ml) at 50-60°, $Na_2S_2O_4$ (4 g) was added in portions during the course of 0.5 hr when there was a rise of temperature which was not allowed to go beyond 70° ; a white precipitate separated out after the addition was complete. The mixture was acidified (congo red) with conc. HCl (6 ml), cooled in ice-bath and the precipitated amino compound was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Yield 0.92 g (70%) m.p. 165-167°. It decomposes on heating, if prolonged, during crystallisation. It was used as such for the next step. Crystallisation of a small specimen from AcOH gave V as colorless needles, m.p. 171-172°. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 6.1 ; N, 6.4. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 59.2 ; H, 5.8 ; N, 6.2%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid* (VI). A mixture of V (2 g) and Ac_2O (10 ml) was warmed on water bath until most of the solid dissolved, and left overnight at room temperature. It was filtered from traces of insoluble material, the filtrate poured into ice-water, vigorously agitated when a precipitate was obtained. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised twice from dil. MeOH to give VI as colorless needles (1.9 g ; 79%), m.p. 200-201°. (Found : C, 58.6 ; H, 5.8 ; N, 5.3. $C_{13}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 58.8 ; H, 5.6 ; N, 5.2%).

7-*Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (VIII). A mixture of VI (6.5 g), $PhNH_2$ (2.5 ml) and PCl_3 (0.7 ml) in toluene (50 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr, cooled and the solid that separated was filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from EtOH gave the hydrochloride of VIII as colorless needles (6.1 g), m.p. 225-226°. It was triturated with 10% Na_2CO_3 aq., filtered, washed with water and crystallised from EtOH to yield VIII as colorless needles (5.5 g ; 69%), m.p. 160-161°. (Found : C, 70.9 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 8.4. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.8 ; H, 5.6 ; N, 8.7%).

4-*Allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-benzamidobenzoic acid* (VII). A solution of V (2 g) in $NaHCO_3$ aq. (40 ml) was treated with $PhCOCl$ (5 ml) and shaken vigorously until solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with water and triturated with 2N HCl. It was again filtered, washed with water followed by a little EtOH and crystallised twice from a large volume of EtOH to afford VII as colorless shining needles (2 g ; 70%), m.p. 225-226°. (Found : C, 66.2 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 4.4. $C_{18}H_{17}O_5N$ requires C, 66.0 ; H, 5.2 ; N, 4.2%).

7-*Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3, 1-benzoxazin-4-one* (X). VII (2 g) was refluxed with Ac_2O (6 ml) for 15 min. and left overnight. It was chilled in an ice-bath and the

colorless needles which separated were filtered, washed with ether to yield X (1.5 g; 85%), m.p. 137-138°. The product was pure enough for use in the next step. A sample crystallised from AcOH melted at 138°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 5.3; N, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.0; N, 4.6%).

(b) V (2.1 g) dissolved in dry pyridine (2 ml) was treated with PhCOCl (1.5 ml) and left overnight. It was poured into ice-water and the solid that precipitated out was collected, washed with water and crystallised from AcOH to give X as colorless needles (1.1 g; 38%), m.p. 137-138°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as in (a).

7-*Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (IX). (a) A mixture of VII (4 g), PhNH₂ (1.75 ml) and PCl₃ (0.5 ml) in toluene (60 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. in an oil bath at 110-120°, cooled and filtered from traces of insoluble material. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure and treated with light petroleum when pale yellow solid (3.5 g) precipitated out. It was triturated with 10% Na₂CO₃ aq., filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dil. MeOH to give IX as colorless needles (3 g; 64%), m.p. 137-138°. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.5; N, 7.1. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3%).

(b) X (2 g) was refluxed with PhNH₂ (0.6 ml) in dry CHCl₃ (20 ml) for 4 hr., the solvent distilled off when almost colorless solid residue was left. On crystallisation from dil. MeOH, IX was obtained as colorless needles (2.3 g; 92%), m.p. 137-138°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen prepared as in (a).

8-*Allyl-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XI). VIII (5 g) suspended in PhNEt₂ (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. in CO₂ atmosphere in an oil bath at 215-220° when a dark solution obtained. It was filtered hot from traces of suspended impurities, cooled and on being left in the frigidiare overnight deposited crystalline solid. It was filtered, washed with benzene followed by ether to give off-white crystals (4.2 g), m.p. 234-235° which was purified by dissolving in 2N NaOH and acidification of the filtered solution with AcOH. Crystallisation from AcOH or EtOH afforded XI as colorless rhombic plates (4 g; 80%), m.p. 238-239°. (Found: C, 70.9; H, 5.4; N, 8.9. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

8-*Allyl-7-hydroxy-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XII). IX (10 g) in PhNEt₂ (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. in CO₂ atmosphere in an oil bath at 220-225°. It was worked up as the preceding compound and the product isolated was crystallised from EtOH to give XII as colorless needles (9 g; 90%), m.p. 188-189°. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 5.1; N, 7.1. $C_{24}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.2; N, 7.3).

7-*Acetoxy-8-allyl-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XIII). A solution of XI (8 g) in dry pyridine (20 ml) was treated with Ac₂O (12 ml) and left overnight. The solution was filtered from traces of insoluble material, poured into crushed ice and the colorless solid that separated was collected, washed with water and crystallised from dil. EtOH to give XIII as colorless needles (7.5 g; 90%), m.p. 165-166°. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 5.7; N, 7.4. $C_{21}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.5; N, 7.7%).

7-*Acetoxy-8-allyl-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one* (XIV). It was prepared as the preceding compound by treating a solution of XII (4 g) in pyridine (10 ml) with

Ac₂O (6 ml). Crystallisation from EtOH furnished XIV as colorless needles (3.5 g; 8%), m.p. 153-154°. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 5.4; N, 6.4. C₂₆H₂₂O₄N₂ requires C, 73.2; H, 5.1; N, 6.5%).

7-Acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-6-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenyl quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV). To a stirred solution of XIII (3 g) in dry CHCl₃ (20 ml) was added dropwise 2% v/v Br₂ in CHCl₃ (31.7 ml; 1 ml ≡ 5.4 ml 0.09N Na₂S₂O₃) until the colour of Br₂ was discharged. The solvent was evaporated at room temperature and the sticky residue when rubbed with a little EtOH or AcOEt-light petroleum solidified. It was filtered, washed with ice-cold AcOEt and crystallised from EtOH to give XV as colorless felted needles (2 g; 47%), m.p. 209-210°. (Found: C, 48.4; H, 4.1; Br, 30.7. C₂₁H₂₀O₄N₂Br₂ requires C, 48.1; H, 3.8; Br, 30.5%).

7-Acetoxy-8-(2', 3'-dibromopropyl)-6-methoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI). It was prepared as the preceding compound by the action of Br₂ in CHCl₃ (19 ml.; 1 ml ≡ 5.6 ml 0.088 N Na₂S₂O₃) on a solution of XIV (2 g) in CHCl₃ (20 ml). The thick gum obtained after evaporating the solvent on trituration with a little EtOH, solidified. It was crystallised from EtOH to yield XVI as off-white needles (1.4 g; 50%), m.p. 172-173°. (Found: C, 52.9; H, 4.1; Br, 27.6. C₂₆H₂₂O₄N₂Br₂ requires C, 53.2; H, 3.7; Br, 27.3%).

2',3'-Dihydro-2,2'-dimethyl-6-methoxy-3-phenylfuro(4',5':7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XXI). XI (1 g) was heated with 48% HBr aq. (15 ml) on water bath for 6 hr, diluted with water and filtered. The residue was triturated with 2N Na₂CO₃, filtered and washed with water. Recrystallisations from dil. MeOH furnished XXI as colorless flakes (0.25 g; 25%), m.p. 190-191°. (Found: C, 71.0; H, 5.4; N, 8.8. C₁₉H₁₈O₃N₂ requires C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

2,2'-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-3-phenylfuro (4',5':7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII). (a) XV (0.8 g; 0.0015 mole) was refluxed in a solution of KOH (0.9 g; 0.015 mole) in EtOH (20 ml) for 2 hr, EtOH (10 ml) distilled off, the solution diluted with water and cooled in ice. The silky colorless needles that separated were filtered, washed with water and dried (0.6 g), m.p. 208-220°. Purification by chromatography of its benzene solution over Al₂O₃ and subsequent recrystallisations from isopropanol furnished XVII as white silky needles (0.4 g; 50%), m.p. 231-232°. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 5.3; N, 8.5. C₁₉H₁₆O₃N₂ requires C, 71.2; H, 5.0; N, 8.7%).

The alkaline filtrate was washed with benzene and acidified with AcOH when a little precipitate was obtained. Recrystallisations from benzene-light petroleum yielded colorless needles, m.p. 195-196°, subsequently identified as XVIII (see below).

(b) A mixture of XXI (0.25 g), diphenyl ether (10 ml) and 1% Pd-C (0.1 g) was refluxed for 12 hr, filtered hot and the filtrate was steam distilled to remove the solvent. The solid residue was crystallised from isopropanol to give XVII as colorless needles (0.15 g; 60%), m.p. 231-232°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as in (a).

2,2'-Dimethyl-6-hydroxy-3-phenylfuro (4',5':7,8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII). XV (0.52 g; 0.001 mole) was added to a solution of KOH (0.56 g; 0.01 mole) in EtOH (15 ml) and left overnight. After refluxing for 2 hr, EtOH (7 ml) was distilled off, the solution diluted with water (20 ml) and washed with benzene (20 ml × 3). The cooled alkaline

solution, on acidification with AcOH, deposited white solid which on recrystallisations from benzene-light petroleum gave XVIII as colorless needles (0.32 g; 80%), m.p. 195-196°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained above as in (a). (Found: C, 70.2; H, 4.7; N, 9.2. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.5; H, 4.5; N, 9.1%).

A slurry of XVIII (0.1 g) in ether (10 ml) was treated with ethereal CH_2N_2 (from 0.5 g N-nitrosomethyl urea) and left overnight. Evaporation of ether left a solid residue which on two crystallisations from isopropanol gave XVII (0.06 g; 60%), m.p. 231-232°, undepressed when admixed with the specimen obtained above as in (a).

2'-Methyl-6-hydroxy-2,3-diphenylfuro(4', 5' : 7, 8)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIX). XVI (1.172 g; 0.002 mole) was refluxed with a solution of KOH (1.2 g; 0.02 mole) in EtOH (30 ml) for 2 hr. on water bath, EtOH (20 ml) distilled off, the solution diluted with water (20 ml) and cooled. The solid that separated was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator (0.2 g), m.p. 205-228°. Repeated crystallisations from isopropanol gave the neutral bromo compound, believed to be XXIII, m.p. 220-230°.

The alkaline filtrate was washed with benzene (20 ml×3), acidified with AcOH and cooled when a white precipitate separated. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator (0.4 g), m.p. 200-201°, with previous sintering at 167-168°. Recrystallisations from AcOEt gave XIX as colorless needles (0.37 g; 50%), m.p. 211-212°. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 4.2; N, 7.4. $C_{23}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.0; H, 4.3; N, 7.6%).

2'-Methyl-6-methoxy-2, 3-diphenylfuro (4', 5' : 7, 8) quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XX). XIX (0.2 g) in ether (20 ml) was treated with an ethereal solution of CH_2N_2 (from 1.5 g of N-nitrosomethyl urea) and kept overnight. The solid residue left after evaporating the ether, was crystallised from isopropanol to yield XX as colorless needles (0.16 g; 76%), m.p. 167-168°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 4.1; N, 7.4. $C_{24}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 75.4; H, 4.3; N, 7.6%).

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
BIHAR UNIVERSITY,
L. S. COLLEGE,
MUZAFFARPUR.

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